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MED-GOLD

Turning climate-related information into added value for traditional **MED**iterranean **GRAPE**, **OL**ive and **DURUM** wheat food systems

Report on the Summer training event n.1 (Deliverable 6.6)

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

In this report the first MED-GOLD training event has been described. Originally planned as a Summer School to be held in Cagliari, Italy from 25 May 2020 to 29 May 2020, it has been converted during spring 2020 into a remotely based training event called the MED-GOLD Living Lab "Turning climate information into value for traditional Mediterranean agri-food systems".

The Living Lab has been conducted as an on-line event for five weeks, from May 25 to June 25, with weekly interactive webinars by speakers across different disciplines and on-line working groups with multidisciplinary teams, supported by scientists from the MED-GOLD experts as mentors.

The report includes the main features of the MED-GOLD Living Lab 2020 including also the necessary steps and the strategy adopted to turn the physical summer school in an online event

With the Living Lab, the project has contributed to the achievement of the following objectives (DOA, PartB Table1.1):

No.	Objective	Yes
1	To co-design, co-develop, test, and assess the added value of proof-of-concept climate services for olive, grape, and durum wheat	
2	To refine, validate, and upscale the three pilot services with the wider European and global user communities for olive, grape, and durum wheat	
3	To ensure replicability of MED-GOLD climate services in other crops/climates (e.g., coffee) and to establish links to policy making globally	X
4	To implement a comprehensive communication and commercialization plan for MED-GOLD climate services to enhance market uptake	
5	To build better informed and connected end-user communities for the global olive oil, wine, and pasta food systems and related policy making	X

1. LIVING LAB CONTENTS

1.1 FROM SUMMER SCHOOL TO LIVING LAB

The initial plan was to hold the first training event as a summer school Cagliari, Italy, in the second half of May 2020 (likely 25-29 May). The island of Sardinia is currently facing severe problems related to climate variability (for example, reduced rainfall over the past 40 years and increased coastal erosion). These impacts clearly affect the typical Mediterranean crops present, that are part of the particular landscape and the regional economy. Hence, Sardinia was considered an appropriate location for the training event, also in the perspective of upscale the MED-GOLD pilot services and test the replicability of the methodologies that the project is developing and implementing.

The **organizing committee** for the Summer School included:

Alessandro Dell'Aquila (M), Luigi Ponti (M) Sandro Calmanti (M) ENEA ; Marta Bruno Soares (F) Univ. of LEEDS; Natalie Garret (F, from beginning of 2020 she changed role and she did not contribute anymore) Michael Sanderson (M), Met Office; Massimiliano Pasqui (M), CNR;

with **technical support** from:

Michela Secci (F); Giuseppe Musu (M), Federico Caboni (M) BeeToBit.

About 20 meetings of the organizing committee have been conducted between June 20, 2019 and June 21, 2020, just before the start of the training.

A possible venue for the summer school has been identified (see <https://www.hostelmarinacagliari.it/>, with an estimated cost of around 1000 €) and other options will be checked during summer 2019. A social event had been organized during the first days (icebreaker, with estimated cost of around 600 €). Travel and stay costs for the Committee should be about 4000 € The expenses incurred for travelling, food, and accommodation of speakers external to MED-GOLD Consortium will be up to 5000 €. The provisional overall cost for this training event was estimated about 11000 €.

The Brochure of the MED-GOLD Summer school is reported in ANNEX A.

At the beginning of the COVID-19 emergency it was decided to convert the Summer School into a remotely based training event called the MED-GOLD Living Lab.

1.2 RATIONALE

The MED-GOLD Living Lab was dedicated to early career scientists and professionals in the areas of climate science, agriculture, economy, social sciences and communication.

The Living Lab has been conducted as an on-line event for five weeks, from May 25 to June 25, with weekly interactive webinars by speakers across different disciplines and on-line working groups with multidisciplinary teams, supported by scientists from the MED-GOLD experts as mentors.

Participants have been challenged by real users of climate information to develop prototype climate services for the agri-food sector, building on the knowledge and skills shared during the event.

Early career scientists and professionals with a wide range of individual profiles have been encouraged to apply and join the multidisciplinary teams: climate scientists, agronomists, software developers (R, Python), economists, social scientists, communication and visual communication experts.

The purpose of the Living Lab was to demonstrate to the participants the MED-GOLD concepts and methodologies to develop climate services as well as become familiar with climate data and tools made available through the Copernicus Climate Data Store (CDS).

1.3 ADVERTISING THE LIVING LAB

The Living Lab was advertised with a dedicate page in the Event section of the MED-GOLD website:

<https://www.med-gold.eu/event/summer-school-2020-turning-climate-information-into-value-for-traditional-mediterranean-agri-food-systems/>

We started advertising the summer school already in December 2019

https://twitter.com/medgold_h2020/status/1250469100574384129?s=20

The official launch of the summer school and the invitation to register has been sent out on February 10th, about one month before the complete lockdown in Italy and all over Europe started:

https://twitter.com/medgold_h2020/status/1226821807438811137?s=20

During the week of April 15, we started advertising the new Living Lab on twitter:

https://twitter.com/medgold_h2020/status/1250469100574384129?s=20

Moreover, the general program has been published in the web-site (Fig.1-1)

Figure 1-1 The program for the MED-GOLD Living Lab 2020.

FIRST MED-GOLD LIVING LAB

Turning climate information into value for traditional Mediterranean agri-food systems

25 May - 25 June 2020

Programme of plenary sessions

Week 1 session #1: Monday 25 May 11.00-13.30 CEST	Week 2 session #2: Thursday 04 June 11.00-13.30 CEST	Week 3 session #3: Thursday 11 June 11.00-13.30 CEST	Week 4 session #4: Thursday 18 June 11.00-13.30 CEST	Week 5 session #5: Thursday 25 June 11.00-13.30 CEST
Getting to know you	Step 1 - Assessing	Step 2- Developing	Step 3 - Testing	Step 4- Implementing & upscaling
Welcome and introduction to the living lab	Assessing vulnerability, decision-making and users' needs for climate services development	Developing climate services for agriculture	Quality assessment focusing on Med-Gold pilot services	Evaluating climate services
Who is who in the room plus questions from the students - virtual social event	Approach adopted to ASSESS the Med-gold pilot services?	Approach adopted to DEVELOP the Med-Gold pilot services	Approach adopted to TEST the Med-Gold Pilot Services	IMPLEMENTING a climate service
Structure of the living lab, speakers and teams introduction	Comfort break	Accessing and using climate data to develop climate services	Visualisation and tools	Technical UPSCALING of climate services
Comfort break	Q&A from groups with the problem-holders	Comfort break	Comfort break	Comfort break
Keynote on climate services	Team work & technical support session, guided by mentors	Team work & technical support session, guided by mentors	Intermediate sprint presentation by the students teams	Presentation of group ideas to the problem holders
Presentation from problem holders			Team work & technical support session,	Wrap up and goodbyes
Discussion of teams with their mentors				

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1.4 MANAGING THE LIVING LAB

Once it has been agreed that the MED-GOLD Summer school should be turned into an online event, a number of possible technical solutions including different platforms have been taken into account.

Figure 1-2 A screenshot for the Amazon Chime Living Lab workspace

For the on-line Living Lab, the identified technical needs were in principle:

- Stable connection
- Possibility of having parallel on-line sessions under the same environment
- A single place also to exchange quick messages (i.e Whatsapp, Slack, etc...)
- Possibility to record the sessions (to be included in the MED-GOLD youtube channel

https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCnpLs45u9oh0uWksH_WCDCw/videos

The usual platform commonly used by the MED-GOLD Consortium Adobe Connect did not have all the functionalities required for the Living Lab and it has been agreed to use Amazon Chime (a screenshot of the landing page of Living Lab workspace is reported in Fig.1-2), with the technical support provided by BeeToBit. This platform uses particularly stable distributed connections and allows a smooth management of different channels (for the organizers, for plenary sessions and for the participants teams) with related rooms dedicated to parallel meetings.

1.5 PARTICIPATION

The registration for the Living Lab has been closed by the 8th of May 2020 with a total of **31 registration** (some of them already acquired before the cancellation of the Summer School in Cagliari). After the deadline a final request of confirming interest to participate in the event has been sent to the people registered and finally **19 people (14 M, 5 F)** have definitely confirmed their willingness (see Table 1-1) .

The participants have been divided in the three teams, balanced in terms of gender, nationality, background.

About 70% of the registered participants have constantly attended all 5 session of the Living Lab and participated actively to the team work.

Table 1-1 List of confirmed participants divided by teams and their participation in each sessions

	Name	Team	Session #1	Session #2	Session #3	Session #4	Session #5
1	Andrea Zedda	Green	1				
2	Emanuele Eccel	Green	1	1	1	1	1
3	Juan carlos Conde Bravo	Green	1				
4	Marina Anić	Green	1	1	1	1	1
5	Meriem Krouma	Green	1	1	1	1	1
6	Nikolaos Mastrantonas	Green	1	1	1	1	1
7	Amen AL-yaari	RisCoff				1	1
8	Antonio Rafael Sánchez-Rodríguez	RisCoff	1	1	1	1	1
9	Hanene Mairech	RisCoff	1	1	1	1	1
10	Luigi Conte	RisCoff	1	1			
11	Roberto Serrano-Notivoli	RisCoff	1				
12	Vincenzo Schiano Di Cola	RisCoff	1	1	1	1	1
13	Andrés Alegría	Re-Wine	1	1		1	1
14	Balakrishnan Solaraju Murali	Re-Wine	1	1	1	1	1
15	Carlo Zucca	Re-Wine	1	1	1	1	1
16	Christiana Olusegun	Re-Wine	1	1	1	1	1
17	Miquel Tomas	Re-Wine		1	1		
18	MUSSA NKUCHA	Re-Wine					
19	Raed Hamed	Re-Wine	1	1	1	1	1
			16	14	12	13	13
		Total	84%	74%	63%	68%	68%

1.6 General Structure

Preliminary Material

Before the event some preliminary material has been sent to the students in order to have a common background for all participants.

1) Three modules of the Copernicus User Learning Service (ULS)

- Introduction to the Copernicus Climate Change Service:
https://uls.climate.copernicus.eu/c/portal/learn-portlet/open_package?plid=638303&oid=1247
- Seasonal Forecasting:
https://uls.climate.copernicus.eu/c/portal/learn-portlet/open_package?plid=638303&oid=1381
- Climate Projections:
https://uls.climate.copernicus.eu/c/portal/learn-portlet/open_package?plid=638303&oid=1670

2) It has been also recommended the vision during the Living Lab of the following modules on the Copernicus (ULS)

- Sectoral Application for Agriculture:
https://uls.climate.copernicus.eu/c/portal/learn-portlet/open_package?plid=638303&oid=1330
- Seasonal forecasts for sectoral impacts:
https://uls.climate.copernicus.eu/c/portal/learn-portlet/open_package?plid=638303&oid=1387

3) Additional resources such as the MED-GOLD infosheets and accepted deliverables and other material (including the contributions presented in the Lab) from the scientific literature available.

Problem-holders

Three Problem-holders have been invited to present a specific problem of their sector: namely Chiara Monotti, Barilla, Italy (Durum wheat/Pasta sector); Antonio Graca, Sogrape Vinhos, Portugal (Grape/Wine Sector) and Ilaria Danesi, Danesi Caffè, Italy (Coffee sector)

The first two are already involved in the MED-GOLD consortium, while Ilaria Danesi has been specifically contacted for the Living Lab, taking advantage of her interest in MED-GOLD activities. It is worth noting that the participation of Ilaria Danesi has been

facilitated by the on-line nature of the event, as in case of a physical meeting her participation would not be possible.

The problem-holders have briefly presented the specific problem in the first session and provide some feedbacks to the students in the session #2 and in case in session#4. During the weeks of the course, the students could interact with the problem-holders by Amazon Chime (by messages or in self-organized meetings) .

Finally, in the last session, Thursday 25 June, the problem-holders have evaluated the work done by the students.

Plenary sessions

The general program of the Living Lab included five plenary sessions plus a number of self organized break-up teams sessions animated by three mentors from the MED-GOLD Consortium: Marta Bruno Soares (Univ Leeds), Sandro Calmanti (ENEA); Massimiliano Pasqui (CNR). After the first introductory session, the other ones have been focused on the 4 main steps of the methodological framework already adopted in MED-GOLD to co-design and co-develop prototypes of climate services (Fig. 1-3). All the material of the Living Lab, including presentations and videos are available in the Living Lab repository <https://www.med-gold.eu/med-gold-living-lab-2020/>

Figure 1-3 Methodological framework presented and discussed during the MED-GOLD Living Lab.

Session #0:

A first preliminary technical session to test the system has been organized for Thursday 18th May open to participants and speakers as well

Session #1:

Figure 1-4 A screenshot for the Amazon Chime Living Lab first session

In this session (See Fig 1-4) the project MED-GOLD has been briefly presented along with the Living Lab and its main learning objectives by Sandro Calmanti (ENEA). Afterwards a very concise presentation of each student (including their background and a key question they would like to assess during the event).

The key-note talk on the European Landscape of Climate Services has been presented by Carlo Buontempo (ECMWF, Chief of C3S and member of the EAC of MED-GOLD).

Finally, three problem holders (namely Chiara Monotti, Barilla, Italy; Antonio Graca, Sogrape Vinhos, Portugal and Ilaria Danesi, Danesi Caffè, Italy) have presented specific problems for their sectors. After the three presentations and the questions time the participants have been discussed in parallel divided in the three teams on which specific problem (Durum wheat/pasta; grape/wine; coffee) they would like to focus during the Living Lab. The program is reported in Fig.1-5.

Figure 1-5 Detailed program for the Session#1, 25 May 2020.

Introduction	Speaker
Welcome and introduction to MED-GOLD (learning objectives included)	Sandro Calmanti
Who is who in the room plus questions from the students - virtual social event	Sandro Calmanti
Structure of the living lab, ground rules for this online event, allocation of mentors to groups, and working in groups	Alessandro Dell'Aquila
Comfort break	N/A
Keynote on climate services	Carlo Buontempo, ECMWF
Presentation from problem holders (3 problem holders/ 15 min each)	All
Discussion of groups with their mentors for selection of which problem they would like to address	N/A

Social event:

In the late afternoon of Thursday, 28th May an online ice-breaker social event. Participants were asked to bring with themselves a drink and a snack to be presented to the other participant (possibly related to the MED-GOLD main agri-food system: durum wheat/pasta; olives/olive oil; grape/wine). In that occasion the problem-holder from the wine Sector, Antonio Graca from Sogrape Vinhos was able to reply to further questions about the problem he presented during the first session.

Session #2:

The Second plenary session (Thursday 04 June, see Fig.1-6) has been focused on the first step of the MED-GOLD methodological framework: the assessment of users' needs in the co-development of climate services (including the MED-GOLD specific experience). At the end of the frontal lectures by Marta Bruno Soares (Univ Leeds) space has been devoted to the team work, supported by mentors.

Figure 1-6 Detailed program for the Session#2, 04 June 2020.

Step 1 - Assessing	Speaker
Introduction and re-cap of previous session	Alessandro Dell'Aquila, ENEA
Co-producing climate services and assessing users'needs	Marta Bruno Soares, University of Leeds
Co-producing & assessing needs in the Med-Gold pilot services	Marta Bruno Soares, University of Leeds
Comfort break	N/A
Team work & technical support session, guided by mentors	N/A
Q&A from groups with the problem-holders	All

Session #3:

The third plenary session (Thursday 11 June, see Fig.1-7) has been focused on the second step of the MED-GOLD methodological framework: co-development of climate services. Ronald Hutjes presented some relevant examples of climate services for the agricultural sector at large. Afterwards some examples from the MED-GOLD specific experience has been shown by Alessandro Dell'Aquila (ENEA) while a presentation on climate prediction and how and where have access to climate data has been held by Massimiliano Pasqui (CNR) At the end of the frontal lectures space has been devoted to the team work, supported by mentors.

Figure 1-7 Detailed program for the Session#3, 11 June 2020.

Step 2- Developing	Presenter
Introduction and re-cap of previous sessions	Alessandro Dell'Aquila, ENEA
Developing climate services for agriculture	Ronald Hutjes, WUN
Developing the Med-Gold pilot services	Alessandro Dell'Aquila, ENEA
Accessing and using climate data to develop climate services	Massimiliano Pasqui, CNR
Comfort break	N/A
Team work & technical support session, guided by mentors	N/A

Session #4:

The fourth plenary session (Thursday 18 June, see Fig.1-8) has been focused on the third step of the MED-GOLD methodological framework: the testing and validation phase. Marta Terrado (BSC) presented some relevant examples on how to visualise and communicate uncertainty in the front-end of climate service. Afterwards some examples on testing and quality assessment from the MED-GOLD specific experience has been shown by Sandro Calmanti (ENEA). At the end of the frontal lectures a space to the teams to present their preliminary work so far done in replying to the problems presented by users in the first sessions.

Figure 1-8 Detailed program for the Session#4, 18 June 2020.

Step 3 - Testing	Presenter
introduce the session, Re-cap of previous sessions	Alessandro Dell'Aquila; ENEA
Communication and visualisation of uncertainty in climate services	Marta Terrado, BSC
Quality assessment focusing on Med-Gold pilot services	Sandro Calmanti; ENEA
Testing the Med-Gold Pilot Services (present the dashboard + feedback loops with users)	Sandro Calmanti; ENEA
Comfort break	N/A
Intermediate sprint presentation by the students teams of the work planned/done feedback from problem holders	All groups
Team work & technical support session, guided by mentors (+ experts?)	N/A

Session #5:

The fifth and final plenary session (Thursday 25 June, see Fig.1-9) has been focused on the fourth step of the MED-GOLD methodological framework: the implementation, the assessment of added value and upscaling of climate services. Natalie Suckall (Univ Leeds) give some suggestions, based on a worldwide experience, on the evaluation of climate service. Afterwards the MED-GOLD specific experience in the technical implementation of pilot services has been presented by Federico Caboni (BeeToBit) and some example of possible upscaling has been shown by Michael Sanderson (Metoffice). At the end of the frontal lectures the three teams presented the work done to the problem-holders.

Figure 1-9 Detailed program for the Session#5, 25 June 2020.

TIME (CEST)	Step 4 - Using	Presenter
11.00-11.15	Welcome, Introducing the session, Re-cap of previous sessions	Alessandro Dell'Aquila, ENEA
11.15-11.45	Evaluating climate services	Natalie Suckall, University of Leeds
11.45-12.00	Implementing a climate service	Federico Caboni, BeeToBit
12.00-12.15	Technical upscaling of climate services	Michael Sanderson, Met Office
12.15-12.30	Feedback	Marta Bruno Soares, University of Leeds
12.30-13.00	Presentation of GREEN team	GREEN team
13.00-15.00	Lunch break	
15.00-15.30	Presentation of RISCOFF team	RisCoff team
15.30-16.00	Presentation of RE-WINE team	RE-WINE team
16.00-16.15	Wrap up and goodbyes	Alessandro Dell'Aquila, ENEA

Team work

The students have worked in three teams groups (see Fig.1-10) during the five weeks of course with the aim of producing one or more of the following outputs:

- write a proposal on how to deal with the problem (one of those presented by the problem holders);
- develop an application or computer code to analyze the problem;
- write a policy brief that frames and helps solve the problem;
- develop a strategic advice document about the problem;
- develop a communication strategy to organize/visualize the information related to the problem.

The student teams have been left free to choose the focus of their work: two teams have chosen the wine problem, while the other one has focused on coffee. On the basis

of problem of interest, each team found an evocative name (RE-WINE, RISCOff, GREEN team) .

Figure 1-10 Notes of a session of Re-Wine Team work, shared by the participants.

Award

Due to the overall high quality of the work done by participants during the Living Lab, it has been agreed by the organization team that MED-GOLD Project would support publications on this experience.

More in detail, MED-GOLD will offer open access fee for up to 3 peer reviewed papers based

- direct output from the work they developed here OR
- a paper that has been developed from the network established during the Living Lab

Rules:

- Max amount: 1000EUR per publication
- At least 75% of authors must be LivingLab 2020 participants
- Deadline for publication August 2021.
- This award has been presented in the last session (see Fig 1-11)

Figure 1-11 A screenshot for the Amazon Chime Living Lab last session

1.7 FEEDBACK FROM PARTICIPANTS

An online feedback form was distributed to participants in the last day of the living lab. The feedback form was developed using SurveyMonkey and aimed at capturing feedback from participants on different aspects such as the content, design, and delivery of the living lab. A total of 11 participants responded to the feedback form.

Overall the feedback received was very positive with all respondents stating that they would recommend this living lab to others. The majority of respondents were positive about the overall content, design and delivery of the living lab (see summary from link provided below). However, the interactive aspects of the living lab could be further improved not only to ensure that the interactions between participants (e.g. to pursue their work group are effective but also in terms of ensuring that the time at which the living lab runs fits with participants' own commitments. Potential ways of overcoming

these could be to e.g. allocate a specific slot during the living lab programme for group work as well as to identify specific dates/time slots to run future living labs together with participants.

The majority enjoyed the opportunity to engage with real-problems and stakeholders, working in multidisciplinary teams and engaging with experts in climate services.

A summary of the feedback collected from the participants is available in ANNEX B:

2. CONCLUSIONS

In this report the first MED-GOLD training event has been described. Originally planned as a Summer School to be held in Cagliari, Italy since the 25 May 2020 to 29 May 2020, it has been converted during spring 2020 into a remotely based training event called the MED-GOLD Living Lab "Turning climate information into value for traditional Mediterranean agri-food systems".

The Living Lab has been conducted as an on-line event for five weeks, from May 25 to June 25, with weekly interactive webinars by speakers across different disciplines and on-line working groups with multidisciplinary teams, supported by scientists from the MED-GOLD experts as mentors.

Participants have been challenged by real users of climate information, which we refer to as *problem holders* during the training, to develop prototype climate services for the agri-food sector, building on the knowledge and skills shared during the event.

Taking into account the circumstances of the COVID-19 emergency and based on the feedbacks by the participants, it could be considered like a successful experiment, that could be also replicated (and further ameliorated) for the second training event, planned for late spring 2021. In particular the organization of an on-line training as allowed the engagement of an external *problem holder* (Ilaria Danesi from Danesi Caffè) who would have been impossible to engage in the Summer School as it was originally planned and who was instrumental in creating interest among the participants and in paving the way for future activities.

As a final remark it is worth highlighting that the organization of a successful on-line training event has implied the saving of significant funds and has resulted in a virtually zero-emission event, compared to a standard summer school with students travelling around Europe while at the time, allowing the achievement of equivalent training objectives.

ANNEX A.

Brochure of the first MED-GOLD Summer school originally planned in Cagliari (Italy) 25-29 May 2020, and then cancelled due to the Covid-19 outbreak

med-gold summer school 2020
turning climate information into value for traditional Mediterranean agri-food systems
Cagliari, Italy • 25th - 29th May 2020

VENUE
Hostel Marina • Scalette S. Sepolcro • Cagliari

REGISTRATION FEE
30,00 €

APPLICATION DEADLINE
March 23rd, 2020

CONTACT
MED-GOLD_summerschool2020@beetobit.com

Confirmed key note lecturers:
Carlo Buontempo
(Chief of Copernicus Climate Change Service, ECMWF)
Ronald Hutjes
(Lead of Copernicus C3S Global Agriculture, Wageningen University & Research)
Roger Street
(Director of the UK Climate Impacts Programme - UKCIP, Environmental Change Institute, University of Oxford)
Experts from the MED-GOLD consortium
(check the website for the full and updated list)

During this interdisciplinary summer school, you'll get to discuss **the latest advances in climate services for agri-food traditional systems** with some of the leaders in the field and be inspired by speakers from wide spread of disciplines.

Supported by experts and working in teams, you will also be **challenged by real users of climate information** to develop a prototype climate service for them, building on the knowledge and skills shared during the summer school.

for more information, including the full programme, visit:
<https://www.med-gold.eu/event/summer-school-2020-turning-climate-information-into-value-for-traditional-mediterranean-agri-food-systems/>

ANNEX B.

A summary of the feedback collected from the participants at the end of the living lab is available here:

<https://www.med-gold.eu/wp-content/uploads/docs/living-lab-2020/All%20summary%20data%20excluding%20personal%20information.pdf>

END OF DOCUMENT

